

Investigation of inductor-based fully on-chip boost converter

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Abstract—This paper presents the efficiency investigation of a fully on-chip DC-DC step-up converter realized in a standard 130 nm CMOS technology and its comparison to previous works. Research is mainly focused on finding the optimum operation point to provide the high output power and conversion efficiency of the on-chip converter solution. The obtained output voltage of 1.2 V shows 98.6 % efficiency of power conversion, and the maximum output power of 6 mW is achieved. Another performed analysis has been focused on impact of inductor properties as well as impact of the control circuit on the main parameters of the developed boost voltage converter.

Keywords—integrated inductor, on-chip inductor, DC-DC, boost, step-up converter

I. INTRODUCTION

Need for creating overall smaller electronic devices is rising every day. Increased mobility and reduced power consumption of recent applications are calling for new approaches in the way of power management and smaller components used in designs. Both of these requirements have to be considered during the designing the circuits that control voltage levels in the whole system. Voltage converters based on high frequency switching of integrated capacitors are widely used circuits in today's devices. Similar approach is promising with using switched inductors. However, inductors are not easy to implement in the integrated form since the miniaturization of inductor has negative effect on its properties.

The most common issues of the inductor integration are connected to high frequencies necessary for operation of converters. The losses in integrated inductor are caused by series resistance and capacitance coupling between metals and substrate, and metals themselves [1], [2], [3]. These effects may result in limited inductance and quality factor of integrated inductors. Characteristics of integrated inductor, therefore strongly influence operation and properties of inductor-based voltage converters.

This work investigates the maximum theoretical conversion efficiency and output power of a fully integrated inductor-based DC-DC boost converter with a pulse frequency modulation (PFM) control circuit. Aim of this work is to investigate the main inductor properties (R_s , L and Q) and their impact on the converter efficiency and output power. Therefore, we considered all parts of the converter being ideal, including the PFM control circuit. Brief introduction to implemented inductor and circuit topology is brought in Section II. Section

III presents results obtained by simulation of converters with PFM control circuit. Here, results obtained for the converter with alternative schematic of a real integrated inductor as well as with the ideal inductor with series resistance are presented. Section IV compares achieved results to a similar solution implemented in the previous work. The last section brings conclusions for investigation of the inductor properties within a DC-DC boost converter with different control circuits used.

II. PROPOSED CONVERTER TOPOLOGY

The topology chosen for integrated DC-DC step-up converter is a conventional boost converter [3] that is shown in Fig. 1. All parts of the circuit were considered being ideal except for the integrated inductor itself. $C1$ is the filter capacitor and R_{load} represents load of the converter. Switch $SW1$ controls charging and discharging of the inductor and is controlled by signal from a PFM control circuit. Another commonly used switch connecting the inductor to the filter capacitor and load was, in our design, replaced by an ideal diode $D1$. This diode has zero threshold voltage to even more suppress the losses on circuit components, especially switching losses caused by switches. Usage of ideal components has resulted in an inability to properly evaluate the area required for the converter design. However, it is assumed that the integrated inductor will occupy a substantially larger area than all other parts of the converter circuit.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the DC-DC step-up converter

Theoretical inductor model, used in the presented circuit,

Fig. 2. Structure of the integrated inductor

is based on a real integrated inductor implemented in a standard 130 nm CMOS technology and was proposed in [4]. The on-chip inductor was measured and its topology, main characteristics and a circuit model were presented in [5].

Shape of the inductor is a square spiral implemented in 5 metal layers with 5 turns. The outer diameter of the integrated inductor stopped at 1.16 mm x 1.16 mm. Thus, the inductor covers area of 1.346 mm². The whole integrated structure is shown in Fig. 2. Main characteristics obtained from measurements of the implemented inductor include series resistance, inductance and quality factor. One new parameter was proposed in [5] as inductance multiplied by quality factor, which shows middle course of these two parameters. Results obtained from measurements of the integrated inductor are summarized in Table I. Alternative schematic model of the inductor was then derived from measurement results. Highest deviation of characteristics of alternative schematic from measurement results was 4.4 %. Schematic model is used as a two-port passive component with the center port left unconnected, and is more closely investigated in [6].

Tab. I. Inductor properties

	f [MHz]	Rs [Ω]	L [nH]	Q []	L*Q [nH]
@Rs _{Min}	50	7.63	33.74	1.38	46.83
@L _{Max}	410	162.42	66.08	1.04	69.25
@Q _{Max}	190	14.96	37.87	3.03	114.86
@L*Q _{Max}	248	23.31	42.43	2.83	120.24

III. ACHIEVED RESULTS

For power voltage converters driven by PFM control circuit using different inductors, we were investigating the point of highest efficiency and output power. In all simulations, the input voltage of 0.6 V was used and conversion ratio was 2. The PFM circuit controls SW1 switch and provides charging of the inductor and holding the voltage value of 1.2 V at the output of the converter. The ON-time of SW1 was chosen in the range from 2 ns to 16 ns. The load of the converter was swept so that the output current through the load resistor was in the range from 0.25 mA to 5 mA. Firstly, simulations of the voltage converter using an alternative

schematic model of real on-chip inductor were performed. Then, ideal inductor was used for better understanding of linkage between inductor and converter properties. Maximum output power and power conversion efficiency were taken into account as the most important parameters of the converter circuit and only inductance, series resistance and quality factor was considered for ideal integrated inductor. Three different values of inductance and series resistance for the ideal inductor were chosen with respect to measurements presented in [4] and other works [5], [7]. The inductance values $L_1 = 36.871$ nH, $L_2 = 42.431$ nH and $L_3 = 66.086$ nH were used. Chosen values of series resistance of the inductor were $R_{s1} = 1$ [Ω], $R_{s2} = 5$ [Ω] and $R_{s3} = 10$ [Ω]. Finally, the value of quality factor of the inductor was then calculated as:

$$Q = \frac{2\pi fL}{R_s} \quad (1)$$

Simulations settings resulted in 10 simulations in total. Circuit designs were simulated in Cadence design environment for 130 nm CMOS technology. All simulation parameters are summarised in Table II.

Tab. II. Simulation parameters

Parameter	Unit	Parameter Value
Input Voltage	V	0.6
Conversion Ratio	-	2
Output Voltage	V	1.2
Output Current	mA	0.25 ÷ 5
On-time range	ns	2 ÷ 16
Series resistance	-	1, 5, 10
Inductance	nH	37.871, 42.431, 66.086

A. Inductor model

Results obtained by simulation of the converter with the on-chip inductor are shown in Fig. 3. Conversion efficiency has reached the maximum of 62.96% when ON-time of switch

Fig. 3. The maximum power conversion efficiency and the output power for model of the real inductor

SW1 was 48.4 ns, switching frequency was 247.7 MHz and the output power of 3.6 mW was reported. The maximum output power of 6 mW was reached at ON-time of 4 ns and the circuit holds it until ON-time reached the value of 16 ns. During this setup, the converter showed the highest efficiency of 50.56 % for 4 ns ON-time and operated at the switching frequency of 118.1 MHz. From all curves in Fig. 3, one can conclude that the power conversion efficiency is indirectly proportional to ON-time of switch SW1, while the maximum output power is rising as ON-time of the switch increases.

B. Ideal inductor with series resistance

For better understanding of dependency of the voltage converter operation on inductor properties, the investigation of boost converter with the ideal inductor using different values of inductance, quality and series resistance was performed. Simulation results obtained for the voltage converter with the ideal inductor with series resistance are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The maximum power conversion efficiency of the

(a) Maximum power conversion efficiency

(b) Maximum output power

Fig. 4. Characteristics of the ideal integrated inductor

(a) $R_s = 1 \Omega$

(b) $R_s = 5 \Omega$

(c) $R_s = 10 \Omega$

Fig. 5. Maximum efficiency for different values of L and R_s

converter is shown in Fig. 4(a), while values of the maximum output power are depicted in Fig. 4(b). Both graphs also show other corresponding variables for the maximum value of the investigated parameter. On the left-hand Y axis, we present L/Q parameter, which is directly linked to the series resistance of the integrated inductor through equation 1.

From Fig. 4(a), one can observe that the converter was able to reach the highest value of efficiency for low ON-time values and high L/Q values. The maximum efficiency of converter over 90% is achieved. Values of the output power were then slightly scattered from the minimal value up to only around 40 % of the maximum possible output power. In Fig. 4(b), it can be observed that the converter reaches the maximum output power of 6 mW in all cases except for very small ON-time values under 4 ns, and for low L/Q ratios under 10 nH. Better results are again reached at higher L/Q values up to over 90%.

Figure Fig. 5 shows the relation between the maximum power conversion efficiency and ON-time of switch $SW1$ for different inductances and series resistances of the ideal inductor. Here, one can clearly observe that the efficiency is indirectly proportional to ON-time value and only slightly relies on the inductance value. Decreasing trend is more observable for higher values of series resistance as well as dependency on the inductance value. Nevertheless, the best efficiency of power conversion is always achieved for small values of ON-time around 2 ns and the highest inductance values. In the best case, power losses reach value less than 2% and the output power was 0.81 mW. At points of the highest power conversion efficiency, the output power was always under 2 mW. In simulations using the ideal inductor with series resistance, one can observe drastic reduction of the switching frequency that can lead to decrease in switching losses on switches in the real circuit. In all simulations, the converter operated in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM). All significant results obtained in the simulations are summarized in Table III.

Tab. III. Significant parameters obtained by simulation

Parameter	Unit	Inductor	L1	L2	L3
η_{max}	%	62.96	95.06	97.71	98.6
$P @ \eta_{max}$	mW	3.6	0.3	0.3	0.6
$F @ \eta_{max}$	MHz	247.7	8.57	6.89	7.57
$T_{on} @ \eta_{max}$	ns	2	2	2.94	2.6
$Rs @ \eta_{max}$	Ω	23.29	1	1	1
$Q @ \eta_{max}$	-	2.84	2.04	1.83	3.14
P_{max}	mW	6	6	6	6
$\eta @ P_{max}$	%	50.56	84.81	80.81	83.19
$F @ P_{max}$	MHz	118.1	233.31	140.55	112.09
$T_{on} @ P_{max}$	ns	4	2	2.91	3.91
$Rs^* @ P_{max}$	Ω	7.59	5	5	5
$Q @ P_{max}$	-	1.35	11.09	7.49	9.3

* Results of simulations with $Rs = 1 \Omega$ are omitted because quality factor reaches unrealistic high values

Tab. IV. Comparison to other work

Inductor		Model	Ideal	Model	Real
Parameter	Unit	PWM		PFM	
η_{max}	%	54.4	97.91	62.96	98.6
$P @ \eta_{max}$	mW	0.8	0.29	3.6	0.6
$F @ \eta_{max}$	MHz	164.4	252	247.7	7.57
$T_{on} @ \eta_{max}$	ns	-	-	2	2.6
$Rs @ \eta_{max}$	Ω	12.83*	3.99*	23.29	1
$Q @ \eta_{max}$	-	2.98	15	2.84	3.14
P_{max}	mW	5.6	6.22	6	6
$\eta @ P_{max}$	%	13.2	91.41	50.56	84.81
$F @ P_{max}$	MHz	100	134	117.1	233.31
$T_{on} @ P_{max}$	ns	-	-	4	2
$Rs @ P_{max}$	Ω	7.65*	4.27*	7.59	5
$Q @ P_{max}$	-	2.41	15	1.35	11.09

* Approximate values calculated from [5]

IV. COMPARISON TO OTHER WORKS

The aim of this research was to investigate feasibility of an integrated inductor towards its application in a conventional boost voltage converter controlled by ideal PFM control circuit. The other works that studied similarly configured circuit controlled by PWM control circuit were published. Comparison of the results achieved within our research to work presented [5] is summarized in Table IV.

From this comparison, one can estimate that the PFM control circuit achieved better results in both evaluated quantities. Firstly, slightly higher values of the maximum efficiency even with higher values of the output power are shown in the upper part of Table IV. Secondly, the maximum simulated value of the output current was never reached for the voltage converter (driven by PWM control circuit) using alternative schematic model of the inductor. The maximum output power achieved for a circuit with the ideal inductor with series resistance and PWM control circuit was higher than for the same setup with the PFM control circuit. In such a case, the efficiency over 91% was achieved. However, the value of the output power was probably affected by ripple of the output signal.

V. CONCLUSION

Feasibility study of a monolithic on-chip DC-DC step up voltage converter with integrated switched inductor was accomplished. All simulations were performed in Cadence design environment in standard 130 nm CMOS technology. Investigation was focused on the evaluation of inductor properties and their effect on electrical and non-electrical properties of the voltage converter. Conclusions were made with respect to two parameters: the efficiency of power conversion and the output power. Topology of the voltage converter was chosen as standard boost converter with ideal components to eliminate losses in circuit. Firstly, we can conclude that for achieving better results from high frequency switching of the inductor used for voltage conversion, it is crucial to maximize quality factor while minimizing series resistance of the inductor. The

inductance value is then of lower importance but it is advised to keep it as high as possible. Secondly, the control circuit may have considerable impact on the converter output signal. The PFM circuit slightly improved operation of converter if compared to PWM circuit. It is assumed that both control circuits are possible to be used for achieving the same required results with adjusted switching frequency and duty cycle of the control signal. Other features (e.g. desired switching frequency, electromagnetic interference, conduction mode, etc.) could be also important for selection of the control circuit. Finally, when comparing results achieved for model of real inductor and ideal inductor with series resistance, it is obvious that other parasitic effects come into account when power is dissipated in the integrated inductor. These other issues should be also explored and the way of their elimination is to be considered during designing the integrated inductors.

Best overall results of the power conversion efficiency were achieved for voltage converter with ideal integrated inductor with series resistance of $1\ \Omega$ and quality of 3.14, driven by PFM control circuit. Converter efficiency reached value of 98.6% and the output power of 0.6 mW was reported. In this case, the converter operated at switching frequency of 7.57 MHz and ON-time of switch SW_1 was 2.6 ns. The switching frequency should be kept low enough to minimize switching losses on switches. The maximum output power of 6.22 mW has reached for the converter circuit with ideal integrated inductor with series resistance around $4.27\ \Omega$ and quality factor of 15, while being driven by PWM control circuit. However, the output power value is affected by ripple of the output signal. In this case, the efficiency of power conversion was 91.41% and circuit operated at switching frequency of 134 MHz. In all simulations, the converter operated in DCM. Conduction mode of inductor was not further investigated and has only information value.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grant APVV 19-0392, the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic under grants VEGA 1/0731/20 and VEGA 1/0760/21, and ECSEL JU under project PROGRESSUS (Agr. No. 876868).

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